
Work Life Balance as a Predictor of Employee Performance: Evidence from the Retail Industry in Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this research is to determine how the performance of PT. Indomarco Prismatama Palembang employees correlates with their work-life balance. Quantitative methods were used in this study, employing simple regression. The subjects of the study are 145 staff members. The results of the data analysis show a positive and highly significant relationship between work-life balance and employee performance ($R = 0.535$; $p = 0.000 < 0.01$). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value of 0.286 indicates that work-life balance contributes effectively 28.6% to employee performance, while other factors outside the study influence 71.4%. Descriptive results show that the majority of workers have a high performance level (65.5%) and a good work-life balance (53.1%). The results indicate that productivity, motivation, and employees' readiness to complete tasks are influenced by the balance between personal and work life. The results of this study support previous findings that organizational support and work-life balance improve an individual's mental health and performance. Therefore, the research hypothesis that there is a positive relationship between employee performance and work-life balance can be accepted.

KEYWORDS: Work–Life Balance; Employee Performance; Retail Industry

INTRODUCTION

The success of a company in achieving its established goals is influenced by a strategic asset known as human resources. The quality of employee performance greatly determines the company's competitive advantage because employees directly play a role in running operations and ensuring the organizational system functions well (Khaeruman, 2024). The work results achieved by someone based on certain quality and quantity standards according to the responsibilities given are called employee performance (Mokosolang et al., 2021). Therefore, performance optimization becomes the main focus in HR management. PT Indomarco Prismatama Branch is a national retail company with a complex organizational structure, featuring various departments such as Finance, Tax, Distribution Center, Human Resources, Development, and Virtual Administration. Each department has different work targets and responsibilities. Attention to detail, punctuality, team coordination, and adherence to company operational standards are all necessary requirements. If these tasks are not balanced with effective HR management, they risk causing high work pressure.

Empirical evidence shows that there are issues with discipline and poor work quality at PT Indomarco Prismatama. Attendance data from January to May 2025 shows a total of 77 absenteeism cases, with the highest absenteeism rates recorded in January and March. Work behaviors such as lack of initiative, working only when supervised by a superior, and completing tasks without paying attention to quality standards were also found. Additionally, the initial survey results indicate that only 25% of employees demonstrate a high level of initiative in solving problems without waiting for directions from their supervisors.

The balanced condition between time, engagement, and satisfaction in work and personal life roles is known as work-life balance (Greenhaus & Allen, 2011). Those who have a good work-life balance tend to have flexible time control, feel satisfied with their relationships with their work and personal life, and can complete tasks in line with the company's goals. Recent studies show that the balance between work and personal life for employees positively correlates with productivity, work engagement, and the psychological well-being of employees (Almurthado, 2024).

However, the results of observations and interviews conducted by employees of PT Indomarco Prismatama indicate a discrepancy between policy and implementation. Most employees still experience tight deadlines and high workloads, even though the company has implemented flexible working hours and leave rights policies. Only thirty percent of the surveyed employees feel they have flexible working hours, and thirty-five percent feel satisfied with the balance between their work and personal lives. This indicates that policies focused on work-life balance are still less effective in improving performance.

Pandiangan (2018) conducted previous research that found the implementation of work-life balance improves job satisfaction and productivity in the manufacturing industry; however, the study did not specifically examine how it directly impacts individual

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performance. Anhar (2025) shows that work flexibility can enhance work engagement and reduce stress. However, he did not consider contextual factors such as workload and company culture. This research is very important because there is a gap between theory and empirical evidence. The purpose of this research is to evaluate the impact of work-life balance on the performance of employees at PT Indomarco Prismatama Branch Palembang. This study not only investigates the direct relationship between the two variables but also provides a contextual overview of how effective the company's policies are in supporting employee productivity and well-being.

According to Koopmans et al. (2014), employee performance consists of two aspects, namely: (1) task performance, which is the ability of employees to complete the tasks or main duties assigned to them; (2) contextual performance, which is the good behavior of employees in activities that do not directly contribute to the organization but support the organization in the context of psychological, social, and environmental work. Grecia et al. (2023) explain that balancing life and work, that is, balancing personal obligations and work without burdening either, can have a positive impact on employee performance. The implementation of fair policies for employees depends on their awareness of how to achieve a balance between their personal life and work in every aspect of their lives. Individual, organizational, and life factors are some of the factors that influence work-life balance (Wulansari, 2023). For individuals, the ability to manage time and stress levels becomes the main components that determine that balance. On the other hand, organizational elements such as work flexibility, workload, and company policies that support employee well-being also contribute to the creation of a healthy work environment (Wicaksana et al., 2020). Additionally, life factors such as family roles and social responsibilities can also influence how an employee balances their personal life with work demands.

Theoretically, the results of this research are expected to serve as a basis for management to improve policies regulating the balance between work and personal life. This will help create a more productive and healthier workplace. Theoretically, this research contributes to the development of studies on human resource management, particularly related to retail organizations in Indonesia.

METHODOLOGY

The employee performance scale and the work-life balance scale are the two measurement tools used in this study. There are 60 items on the Work-Life Balance scale and 60 things on the Employee Performance scale. Following a trial of the measurement tools, the researcher examined the validity and reliability of both measures. The next step is to perform validity and reliability tests on the measuring device based on the information gathered from earlier trials. The statistical software SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science), version 26 for Windows, is used to conduct this testing. The alpha reliability value for the Employee Performance scale was around 0.978, while the alpha reliability value for the Work-Life Balance scale was approximately 0.981. Given that both scales' reliability scores are near to 1.00, it can be concluded from the data that they have good measurement consistency. This indicates that the work-life balance and employee performance scales are appropriate for use as research tools.

Ninety-five employees, or 65.5%, of the 145 employees of PT. Indomarco Prismatama Palembang who served as research subjects had high employee performance, whereas the other fifty employees, or 34.5%, had bad performance. These findings suggest that PT. Indomarco Prismatama personnel generally exhibit strong employee performance. The high degree of employee performance in this study shows that workers can fulfill their duties and responsibilities as best they can in accordance with the company's standards. High performance is a reflection of an employee's capacity to meet goals, uphold standards of quality, and accept accountability for their work.

According to Mangkunegara (2017), employee performance is the outcome of a person's efforts in terms of the amount and quality of work completed in accordance with the duties assigned. 77 people, or 53.1% of the 145 employees of PT. Indomarco Prismatama Palembang who were used as research subjects, had a great work-life balance, while the remaining 68 employees, or 46.9%, had a low one. The high degree of work-life balance found in this study suggests that workers can successfully manage the demands of both their personal and professional lives. Workers who have a healthy work-life balance are typically able to balance their personal and professional obligations without interfering with one another. Work-life balance, according to Greenhaus and Powell (2006), is the state in which people feel content and balanced in their roles at work and in their personal lives. Workers who have a healthy work-life balance are typically less stressed and more productive.

According to the p-values of the instruments, which are Employee Performance $p = 0.112$ ($p > 0.05$) with KS-Z 0.098 and Work-Life Balance $p = 0.342$ ($p > 0.05$) with KS-Z 0.077, the results of the Kolmogorov-Smirnov normality test using the Monte Carlo approach for both data obtained through measuring instruments developed by the researcher are said to be normally distributed because they meet the criterion of $p > 0.05$. With a F value of 68.655 and $P = 0.054$, the F value is a coefficient that shows the link between the independent and dependent variables. Work-Life Balance (X) and Employee Performance (Y) have a linear association, according to the P value = 0.054 (< 0.05) in the preceding table. Work-Life Balance and Employee Performance have a correlation of $R = 0.535$, $P = 0.000$ ($P < 0.01$). With a R Square value of 0.286 (28.6%) and a $(R) = 0.535$, this result shows that work-life balance and employee performance at PT. Indomarco Prismatama Palembang are highly significantly correlated.

This indicates that work-life balance and employee performance are positively correlated. The R Square value of 0.286 indicates

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that work-life balance contributes 28.6% to employee performance, while the remaining 71.4% is influenced by other factors not examined in this study.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the data and research discussion, it can be concluded that there is a positive and significant relationship between work-life balance and employee performance at PT. Indomarco Prismatama Palembang. The results of the simple regression test show that the research hypothesis is accepted with a correlation coefficient value of $R = 0.535$ and a significance value of $P = 0.000$ ($P < 0.01$). This means that employee performance is higher if they have a balance between work and life.

This result is in line with the theory that states that a balance between work life and personal life can maintain employees' mental and physical health as well as motivation, thereby impacting on productivity improvement (Eldon, 2024)

Employee performance is influenced by the effective contribution of work-life balance by 28.6% ($R^2 = 0.286$). Other factors not examined in this study account for 71.4%. Additionally, descriptive results show that the majority of employees fall into the high-performance category (65.5%) and have a relatively high level of work-life balance (53.1%). This indicates that the perception of organizational support, time management skills, and the balance between work demands and personal life are factors contributing to improved work performance.

Theoretically, the findings of this research support the idea that the balance between work and personal life contributes to employees' psychological health, motivation, and productivity. Practically, these findings indicate that companies should maintain and enhance policies and facilities that support work-life balance, such as work flexibility, a comfortable work environment, and managerial support to ensure that all employees can perform at their best.

Asari (2022) The research results show that WLB improves employee performance and job satisfaction. WLB is also shown to be a mediating variable that connects WLB with employee performance. This study also emphasizes that companies should pay attention to their employees' work-life balance by providing flexible work schedules and comfortable workplaces. This research differs from previous ones due to the methods used and the extent of the analysis. Furthermore, the research conducted by Itryah (2022) aims to study how work-life balance and gratitude affect female teachers. The results show that more work-life balance leads to more gratitude among female teachers.

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